

Supporting information

Immobilization and Stabilization of an Engineered Acyltransferase for the Continuous Biosynthesis of Simvastatin in Packed-Bed Reactors

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SUPPORTING MATERIALS

LovD-BuCh2 sequence

Table S1. LovD-BuCh2 amino acid sequence.

Variant	Sequence (Inserted mutation with respect to wild-type LovD are highlighted in bold red)
LovD-BuCh2 (14)	MGSIIIDAAAAADPVVLMETAFRKAVKSRQIPGAV LM ARDASGNLNYTRCFGARTVRRDENNQLPPLQVDTP CRLASATKLLTTIMALQCMERGLVDLDETVDRLLPDLSAMPVLEGFDDAGNARLRERRGKITLRHLLTHTS GLSYVFLHPLLREY VA QGHLSAEKFGIQ NR FAPP LV NDPGAEWIYG GI DWAGKLVERATGLDLEQYLQE NICAPLGITDMTFKLQQRPDMLARRAD M THRNSADGRRLRYDD T VYFR VD GEECFGGQGVF S PGSYMKVLH SLLKRDGLLLQPQTVDLMFQPALEPRLEEQMNQHMDASPHINYGGPMPMVLRRSFGLGGI I ALEDLDGENW RRKGS M TFGGGPNI I WQIDPKAGLCT L VFFQLEPWNDPVCRDLTRTFEHAIYAQYQ Q G

SUPPORTING METHODS

Expression of LovD-BuCh2

The plasmid encoding the His-tagged LovD-BuCh2 (Table S1) variant was transformed into chemically competent *E. coli* strains DH5 α and BL21 through heat shock for plasmid propagation and recombinant protein expression, respectively.¹ Single colonies of *E. coli* containing a plasmid encoding LovD-BuCh2 were inoculated into 3 mL of Lysogeny broth (LB) medium containing 30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin. Cells were grown overnight at 37 °C with shaking at 250 rpm. The culture was diluted 1:50 into 50 mL of LB medium containing 30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of kanamycin and the culture was grown until OD_{600nm} reached 0.6-0.8. At that point, the protein expression was induced by adding isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) to a final concentration of 0.1 mM and the culture was incubated overnight at 21°C with shaking at 250 rpm. Cells were collected by centrifugation (2057 xg for 30 min at 4 °C) and cell pellet was resuspended with 5 mL of 50 mM HEPES buffer at pH 8. Cells were lysed by sonication on ice and cell debris was removed by centrifugation (12857 xg for 30 min).

Calculation of immobilization parameters

The immobilization parameters characterized in this study were calculated as follows:

The load is the mass of immobilized protein per gram of carrier.

$$\text{Load (mg g}^{-1}\text{)} = (\text{offered protein (mg mL}^{-1}\text{)} - \text{protein in supernatant (mg mL}^{-1}\text{)}) \times \frac{\text{immobilization volume (mL)}}{\text{carrier mass (g)}} \quad (1)$$

The immobilization yield (Ψ) is defined as the percentage of the offered enzyme that is immobilized on the carrier. Offered protein and protein in supernatant were calculated by measuring the intensity of SDS-PAGE bands that correspond to LovD-BuCh2 (Mw: 46 kDa) using BSA as standard for the protein calibration curve.

$$\Psi = \frac{\text{offered protein (mg mL}^{-1}\text{)} - \text{protein in supernatant (mg mL}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{offered protein (mg mL}^{-1}\text{)}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The recovered activity (RA) is defined as the measured enzyme activity per gram of carrier and is expressed in U g⁻¹.

The immobilized specific activity (iSA) is defined as the activity per mg of immobilized enzyme.

$$\text{iSA (U mg}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{RA (U g}^{-1}\text{)}}{\text{Load (mg g}^{-1}\text{)}} \quad (3)$$

The relative recovered activity (rRA) is defined as the ratio between the specific activity of the immobilized and the free enzyme ($SA_{\text{free enzyme}}$).

$$\text{rRA} = \frac{\text{iSA}_{\text{immobilized enzyme}}}{\text{SA}_{\text{free enzyme}}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Protein labeling with fluorescent probes

A pure enzyme solution (purified using AG-Co²⁺ and eluted with 300 mM imidazole) was diluted in 100 mM of sodium bicarbonate buffer at pH 8.5 and mixed (1:10 molar ratio) with either rhodamine B isothiocyanate (RBITC) or fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) solutions in DMSO (10 mg mL⁻¹) and incubated for 1 h at 25 °C in the darkness. The labeled enzyme was filtered off using a tangential ultrafiltration unit (10 kDa) and washed with 50 mM HEPES at pH 8 until no coloring was observed in the filtered solution. 1 mL of the pure fluorophore-labelled LovD-BuCh2 was diluted (1:10) and immobilized on different carriers as previously described.

Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM) and imaging and analysis

The localization and distribution of fluorophore-labelled LovD-BuCh2 throughout the different supports were analyzed with a confocal microscope Spectral ZEISS LSM 880 equipped with an excitation laser ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 561 \text{ nm}$ for RBITC) and emission filter (LP505 and LP565, respectively). Confocal images were obtained using 20x (numerical aperture = 0.5) and 40x (numerical aperture = 0.6) objectives. For quantitative assessment of protein infiltration into the porous structure of the carriers, we processed CLSM acquired images to obtain a normalized fluorescence intensity radial profile of single beads using FIJI software (**Figure S2.a,b**). Subsequently, we developed a single-particle analysis algorithm that was implemented in the above-mentioned image processing program. The developed plugin automatically performs a Gaussian fit on the normalized fluorescence intensity radial profile of every single bead of the confocal image under analysis (**Figure S2.c**). Then, the plugin searches for the fitted data point that corresponds to the radius coordinate ($x_{50\%}$), where fluorescence is the 50% of the maximum normalized fluorescence fitted peak ($y_{50\%}$). Then, $x_{50\%}$ is subtracted from the radius of the analyzed bead to obtain the infiltration distance (μm).

Raman spectroscopy and microscopy

Raman spectra and maps were acquired using a confocal Raman microscope (alpha 300R, WITec GmbH) which is equipped with four fiber-coupled excitation sources (488, 532, 633, and 785 nm) and 2 fiber-coupled, lens-based spectrometers optimized for visible and near-infrared range, a motorized scanning stage hooked with a piezo-driven scanning platform for high-precision imaging. Raman spectra were collected from solid (dry) samples under excitation with a 532 nm laser with a power of 65-50 mW focusing through a 20x (numerical aperture = 0.5) or through a 50x (NA= 0.75) objective using the spectrometer of 600 mm focal length, a 300 lines mm⁻¹ grating and a back-illuminated EMCCD camera with 1600 x 200 pixel. For single-point Raman spectra, the integration time was set to 0.2 s and 10 spectra were accumulated and averaged. Alternatively, averaged Raman spectra were also measured by scanning over a determined area and taking single-point spectra with a step size of 1 μm in x and y, an integration time of 50 ms or 100 ms, and averaging the spectra over the whole area. The local distribution of components in the sample can be visualized by chemical imaging. For this application, the Raman maps were created by plotting the Raman intensity of the fingerprint as a function of the position. WITec Suite5/5+ Software (WITec GmbH) was used to process and analyze the data. First, cosmic rays and the background noise were removed, and afterward the True Component Analysis tool implemented in the software Project 5+ package was applied to find and identify (different) components. The component spectrum found can be assigned to a color and the corresponding fingerprint spectrum intensity to a color scale. The plot of each measured pixel (x, y position) as a function of the component and its intensity results in a false-color image showing the local distribution and the concentration of components. Before plotting the image was smoothed by using a 3x3 median filter.

Analysis of intrinsic protein fluorescence

70 μg of LovD-BuCh2 both in solution and immobilized on different supports were resuspended in 50 mM HEPES at pH 8 and placed in a 96-well dark plate before and after incubating for 4 h at 40 °C. Samples were excited at 280 nm to acquire emission spectra that range between 300 and 500 nm with a bandwidth of 5 nm.

Protein fluorescence anisotropy measurements

Either a solution or a suspension containing 3 ng of soluble or immobilized FITC-labelled LovD-BuCh2, respectively, was added to a 96-well dark plate and fluorescence anisotropy was measured in a BioTek Microplate Reader Synergy. Anisotropy values were calculated using the following equation:

$$r = \frac{I_z - I_y}{I_z + I_y} \quad (5)$$

where I_z is the parallel intensity and I_y is the perpendicular intensity. Anisotropy values of immobilized LovD-BuCh2 were normalized to the anisotropy of free LovD-BuCh2. Values lower than 1 mean that the immobilized enzyme has a higher rotational tumbling than the free enzyme, while values higher than 1 mean that the immobilized enzyme has a lower rotational tumbling than the free enzyme.

Thermal inactivation assays

Biocatalysts were weighted (125 mg of LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺ at 1.1 mg g⁻¹ support, 130 mg of LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co²⁺/E at 1.06 mg g⁻¹ support and 405 mg of LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 at 0.36 mg g⁻¹ support) and resuspended in 500 μL of 50 mM HEPES 10 mM

MgCl₂ at pH 8 for their further incubation for 1 h at different temperatures (25, 37, 40, 45, and 50 °C). After incubation, 100 μL of each resuspension (quintuple replicas with 0.138 mg mL⁻¹ of enzyme each) were added to 100 μL of reaction mixture (3 mM MJA, 2 mM DMB-SMMP and 2 mM 2,2'- dithiodipyridine (2-DTDP) in 50 mM HEPES 10 mM MgCl₂ (pH 8) and 10% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)) and the activity was measured in 96-well plates with the enzymatic spectrophotometric assay previously described. The free and immobilized enzymes were also incubated at 40 °C and samples were withdrawn at times (0; 15; 30; 60; 120 and 240 minutes) of incubation and analyzed with the same assay described above.

Stability assay in DMSO

125 mg of the immobilized LovD-BuCh₂ and 125 μL of its free (0.25 mg x mL⁻¹) counterpart were mixed with 500 μL of 40% DMSO in 50 mM HEPES 10 mM MgCl₂ at pH 8. Samples were withdrawn at different times and their activity was measured with the enzymatic spectrophotometric assay described in the main manuscript. Residual activity was plotted as a function of the incubation time (Figure S3)

Productivity and operational metrics in flow

Different parameters such as residence time (τ), space-time yield (STY), specific productivity (SP), and enzyme total turnover number (TTN) were calculated according to the following equations:

$$\tau = \frac{\text{Reactor volume}}{\text{Flow rate}} \quad (6)$$

$$STY = \frac{[\text{Product}]}{\tau} \quad (7)$$

$$SP = \frac{STY}{[\text{enzyme}]} \quad (8)$$

$$TTN = \frac{\text{mol Product}}{\text{mol enzyme}} \quad (9)$$

Sustainability metrics calculation

The sustainability metrics to assess how sustainable the SVA synthesis is were calculated as follows: ²

$$E \text{ factor} = \frac{\text{total reagent mass}}{\text{total product mass}} \quad (10)$$

where E factor is the environmental factor.

$$SF = 1 + \frac{\text{stoichiometric mass}}{\text{mass of all reagents}} \quad (11)$$

where SF is the stoichiometric factor. This parameter means the excess of reagents regarding the limiting reagent.

$$AE = \frac{\sum MW_{\text{products}}}{\sum MW_{\text{reagents}}} \quad (12)$$

where AE is the atom economy, that estimates the number of reagents (substrates, solvents and catalysts) that will be incorporated into the final desired product.

$$MP = \frac{\text{total product mass}}{(\text{total reagent mass})_{n \text{ cycles}}} \quad (13)$$

where MP is the mass productivity. MP is inversely related to E factor.

$$RME = \frac{\text{total product mass}}{(\text{total reagent mass})_{1 \text{ cycle}}} \quad (14)$$

where RME is the reaction mass efficiency.

SUPPORTING RESULTS

Protein expression, immobilization and purification

Figure S1. Sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) for protein expression and immobilization of LovD-BuCh2 on different carriers. CE: Crude Extract. FT: Flow-through. C: Carrier before elution. E: Eluted protein. MW: molecular weight marker. In all cases the eluted fraction (E) should show a protein band corresponding to LovD-BuCh2 as thick as the band observed in CE lane, which means that all the immobilized protein is eluted with imidazole. This only happens in the case of AG-Co²⁺, demonstrating that the immobilization is fully reversible. In contrast, AG-Co²⁺/E and EziG1 must establish additional interaction that cannot be broken under SDS-PAGE denaturing conditions. BSA: Bovine Serum Albumin, used as titration curve to determine LovD-BuCh2 concentration in each protein fraction.

Enzymatic spectrophotometric assay

Scheme S1. LovD-BuCh2 thioesterase spectrophotometric assay. DMB-SMMP: α -dimethylbutyryl-*S*-methyl-mercaptopropanoate. SMMP: *S*-methyl-mercaptopropanoic acid. 2-DTDP: 2,2'-dithiodipyridine.

Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM) imaging and analysis

Figure S2. Explanatory illustration of infiltration distance calculation. **(a)** Representation of fluorescence radial profile of a single microbead in a confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) image. **(b)** Obtained normalized fluorescence intensity radial profile (R represents the particle radius) and **(c)** normalized fluorescence intensity radial profile (grey continuous line) together with the corresponding Gaussian fit (yellow dots) and explanatory illustration of infiltration distance estimation derived from the obtained fitted radial profile.

Figure S3. Confocal fluorescence 3D profiles of single beads (top) of AG-Co²⁺ (a), LovD-AG-Co²⁺/E (b) and @EziG1 (c) with the RhB-LovDBuCh2 on them. X and Y axis are the space coordinate, while Z axis represents the intensity of the fluorescence at each pixel. 2D micrographs of brightfield and red fluorescence channel were also recorded for empty particles (bottom).

Thermal stability analysis

Table S2. Kinetic inactivation constant (k_i) and half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of free LovD-BuCh2 and immobilized in different carriers and incubated at 40 °C for 1 h.

Biocatalyst	k_i	$t_{1/2}$
Free LovD-BuCh2	1.50 (±0.05)	0.46 (±0.01)
LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co ²⁺	0.74 (±0.06)	0.93 (±0.03)
LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co ²⁺ /E	0.29 (±0.07)	2.43 (±0.06)
LovD-BuCh2@EziG1	0.37 (±0.06)	1.85 (±0.05)

Enzyme stability in DMSO

Figure S4. Inactivation of free and immobilized LovD-BuCh2 in DMSO. The different biocatalysts were incubated with 40% DMSO at pH 8 and 25 °C.

Structural flexibility and conformational studies on immobilized LovD-BuCh2

Table S3. Anisotropy values of free LovD-BuCh2 and immobilized in different carriers.

Biocatalyst	Anisotropy
Free LovD-BuCh2	63.0 (± 1.4)
LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co ²⁺	126.7 (± 4.1)
LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co ²⁺ /E	189.5 (± 7.2)
LovD-BuCh2@EziG1	153.7 (± 1.7)

Figure S5. Spectra of LovD-BuCh2 intrinsic protein fluorescence (280 nm). Panels (a), (c), (e), (g) Relative fluorescence units (RFU) vs λ whereas panels (b), (d), (f) and (h) show the spectra normalized to the maximum RFU. Panels (a-b) show the spectra of free LovD-BuCh2. Panels (c-d) show the spectra of LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co₂⁺. Panels (e-f) show the spectra of LovD-BuCh2@AG-Co₂⁺/E. Panels (g-h) show the spectra of LovD-BuCh2@EziG1.

UPLC-MS spectra of SVA synthesis

Figure S6. (a) Ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) spectra of a crude mixture after 24 h reaction with 1 μM of enzyme, 3 mM monacolin J acid (MJA) and 2 mM α -dimethylbutyryl-*S*-methyl-mercaptopropionate (DMB-SMMP) (in red), a pure sample of 2 mM simvastatin acid (SVA) (in green) and a pure sample of 3 mM MJA (in blue). The peak at 1.8 min is assigned to MJA and the peak at 7.0 min is assigned to SVA. (b), (c) Mass spectrometry (MS) spectra of a crude mixture after 24 h reaction with 1 μM of enzyme, 3 mM MJA and 2 mM DMB-SMMP (negative-ion mode). The peak of 436.246 in (b) corresponds to SVA mass and the peak of 337.164 in (c) corresponds to MJA mass.

Continuous synthesis of SVA with a LovD-BuCh2@EziG1 packed-flow reactor

Figure S7. MJA yield (%) after maximum conversion was achieved in a CFP at 10 and 100 μL min⁻¹ with 1 μM of enzyme and 1 mM of SVA.

Table S4. Continuous flow processes calculated parameters, where τ_R is the residence time and STY is the space-time yield.

Reactor	MJA/DMB-SMMP ratio	τ_R (min)	Maximum SVA yield (%)	STY (mg SVA mL ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	Specific Productivity (SP) (mg SVA mg enzyme ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)
CFP-1	1:2	12.5	69.7	2.92	10.74
CFP-2	3:2	23.1	70	1.65	6.05
CFP-3	3:2	12.5	100	4.61	16.95

Sustainability metrics

Figure S8. E factor dissection considering only the contribution of reagents, solvents (excepting water) and catalyst.

Referencias

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